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Pedagogical Guidelines for Integrating Digital Storytelling into the personal, social, and emotional development (PSED) learning area of Pakistan's National Curriculum for Early Childhood Education (ECE)

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ABSTRACT

From ancient cave paintings to modern podcasts, stories have played a fundamental role in shaping human culture and values. The advent of digital storytelling marks a new chapter in this rich tradition of storytelling, influencing our development, communication, and skills. In this era of technological advancement, available dynamic tools pave the way for innovative teaching methods. This doctoral research explores the untapped potential of digital storytelling in the curriculum and assesses its integration as a strategic pedagogical tool. Employing a qualitative methodology, this study analyzed Pakistan's SNCECCE to identify competencies of personal, social, and emotional development (PSED) key learning area. This analysis has supported crafting pedagogical guidelines aimed at the effective use of digital storytelling tools and for the purpose of students' learning and development. This research concluded by suggesting pedagogical guidelines for effectively integrating this dynamic teaching approach of digital storytelling tools and using them for the purposes of students' learning and development. The recommendations of pedagogical guidelines with PSED bring innovation in the teaching practices and elevate the students' learning experiences.

Keywords: Digital Storytelling, Emotional Development, Early Childhood Education, Personal Growth, Social Development, Sncecce, Pedagogical Guidelines

INTRODUCTION

Storytelling has influenced human cultures and values from the time of cave paintings to the modern era of podcasts. In every era, stories have served as a means of development, particularly in social, emotional, moral, and cognitive development from the early years (Pellowski, 1977; Piaget, 1969). In addition, Storytelling in the early years contributes to a child's holistic development (Narvaez, 2002). The traditional way of telling stories has transformed with the emergence of technology, leading to a new trend known as digital storytelling (DST).

Digital storytelling was first introduced by Joe Lambert and Dane Atchley in the late 1980s by initiating the Center for Digital Storytelling (CDS). This center aimed to provide skills and knowledge for developing digital stories (Robin, 2008). Digital storytelling is the combination of digital tools such as images, text, audio, video, and animation with traditional oral stories (Preradovic, Lesin & Boras, 2016). Numerous studies highlight the role of digital storytelling for bringing innovation in education and teaching and learning practices through the integration of video and audio tools for telling stories. Moreover, this digital storytelling approach is also valuable for children's learning and development in the early years (Fajrie, Sutono, Purbasari, Mustofa, & Faresta, 2025; Farooq, Shahabullah, & Hussain, 2025; Farmer, 2004). However, the majority of the studies have been conducted in the Western context, with limited research focusing on the Pakistani context.

Thus, the present study aims to explore the integration of digital storytelling in the Early Childhood Education (ECE) Classroom by aligning it with the SNCECCE, Pakistan. The SNCECCE was revised in 2020 by the Government of Pakistan to standardize the curriculum in all schools across Pakistan (Sameul Hall, 2023). The SNCECCE consists of seven key learning areas, including personal, social, and emotional development (PSED), language and literacy, basic mathematical concepts, the world around us, physical development, health, hygiene and safety, and creative arts. However, the present study focuses on the first learning area, personal growth and socio-emotional domains, towards DST integration.

Thus, this study is part of a PhD research dissertation, suggesting pedagogical guidelines towards the digital storytelling integration with all seven key learning areas of SNCECCE. However, this paper presents the pedagogical guidelines towards digital storytelling integration with the PSED learning area only. The purpose of selecting this area is that it consists of competencies related to social interaction, personal identities, and emotional expressions, as well as moral and religious values, which are essential domains for a child's development in the early years.

Therefore, this paper entails the pedagogical guidelines for integrating digital storytelling tools such as video, audio, animation, written story or ebook, and sound, along with using digital stories for the purpose of students' development and learning, including students' engagement, literacy skills, diverse learning needs support, and technology integration.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The general objective of this study is to develop pedagogical guidelines for integrating digital Storytelling tools and using them for students' learning and development in the ECE classrooms, aligned with the PSED domain of the SNCECCE. This study has the following specific objectives:

To identify the competencies of the personal growth and socio-emotional domains of the SNCECCE that are suitable for integrating DST tools and using them for students' learning and development purposes.

To formulate comprehensive pedagogical guidelines for using DST tools and using them for students' growth and education purposes in the ECE classroom.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This research employed a qualitative method to explore the competencies of PSED domains, to suggest pedagogical guidelines for integrating digital storytelling tools and using them for students' development and learning purposes. Thus, this study has the following questions:

Which competencies of the SNCECCE's PSED domains are suitable for integrating DST tools and using them for students' growth and learning?

How can comprehensive pedagogical guidelines be formulated for effective integration of digital Storytelling tools and for students' learning and development with PSED domains?

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study was restricted to a qualitative document analysis and explored only one key learning area, which is the PSED domain of the SNCECCE. Moreover, this research was limited to the Early Childhood Education classrooms and suggested pedagogical guidelines for the Early Childhood Education teachers and facilitators. Additionally, this study was confined to four purposes for using digital storytelling in the classroom, including students' engagement, literacy skills, diverse learners' needs, and technology integration. However, the other objectives, such as digital stories for mathematical concepts, moral values, etc, are not included in this study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many studies have explored the significance of stories and DST, particularly its role for educational development, teaching, and learning processes (Ugap et al., 2025; Handayani, Siagian, Khayati & Hayati, 2024; Ahmed, Inam & Saif, 2023; Rodríguez et al., 2021; Smeda, Dakich, and Sharda, 2014). The majority of literature has focused

on the use of digital storytelling for enhancing students' motivation, creativity, language development, thinking abilities, and social interactions (Farooq, Shahabullah & Hussain, 2025; Asmayawati, 2023; Zarifsanaiey et al., 2022; Rahiem, 2021).

Digital storytelling is also beneficial for children's holistic development from their earliest years. Holistic development includes physical, social, emotional, cognitive, moral, and spiritual development (Sameul Hall, 2023; UNICEF, 2018). Numerous studies have highlighted the use of digital storytelling for children's social, emotional, and moral development. For instance, DST is helpful for emotional expressions, boosts confidence, and develops a sense of belonging as well as improves social and emotional skills (Behera & Acharya, 2025; Khan et al., 2025; Zarifsanaiey, 2022; O'Byrne, 2018; Nair, Yusof & Hong, 2014; Robin, 2008). A study conducted by Khowaja, Shaheen & Kang (2025) analyzed the use of DST for moral values by reviewing competencies of values outlined in SNCECCE's personal growth and socio-emotional domains.

Pakistan's SNCECCE document was used for analysis. This curriculum was revised in 2020 to provide an equal and unified curriculum to all nations. The curriculum was designed based on the Prime Minister's vision, "one system of education for all, in terms of curriculum, medium of instruction, and a common platform of assessment" (Ministry of Federal Education and Professional Training, 2020). The earlier curriculum was designed in 2007, with a revision in 2017 in Punjab and 2018 in Sindh. There are seven key learning areas specified in this curriculum, of which the PSED domain was focused on in this study for drafting pedagogical guidelines for digital storytelling integration.

Pedagogical guidelines refer in this study to provide techniques to the teachers for integrating DST in the ECE classroom in alignment with the SNCECCE, Pakistan. However, numerous studies suggested guidelines for DST integration in ECE classrooms. For instance, the European Commission (n.d.) entailed guidelines for DST integration with curriculum, planning, and assessment. However, this integration of DST is for the European ECE curriculum. Similarly study done by Ugap et al. (2025) analyzed almost 30 articles related to DST and concluded that DST has the potential to shift traditional approaches to a more engaging and modern learning environment. Their study provided a framework for educators and policymakers to embed DST in teaching and learning processes, though it focused on all levels and mentioned the impact of DST on thinking, creativity, engagement, and literacy skills. Pedagogical guidelines in this study recommended the digital storytelling tools and using them for students' development and education purposes. Several past studies emphasized the use of video and audio tools of digital storytelling in the classroom as they provide visual and oral effects to the children, respectively (Khan et al., 2025; Yu & Wang, 2025; Ng et al., 2022). Further, these studies highlighted the role of video and audio-based stories for social interactions and emotional expressions (Khan et al., 2025; Delahey Childcare, 2024; Undheim, 2020).

Thus, the prior studies provided insights towards DST integration; however, these guidelines generally explored the broader use of DST rather than the integration of DST tools for growth and learning. Moreover, these studies did not explore the integration of DST with key learning areas of ECE as outlined in SNCECCE, Pakistan. In addition, most of these studies were done in a Western context, while not considering the ECE context in Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research method and a document analysis tool for exploring the competencies of the PSED domains outlined in the SNCECCE, Pakistan. This research aims to investigate suitable competencies and suggest pedagogical guidelines for digital storytelling integration of their tools and students' learning and development purposes, with the personal growth and socio-emotional domains. Thus, this design helped provide recommendations for pedagogical guidelines for effective use of digital storytelling tools and for students' learning and development in the Early Childhood classrooms by aligning with this key learning area of the SNCECCE, Pakistan.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The data was collected through document analysis of the SNCECCE, Pakistan, focusing on the competencies of the PSED domain. Thus, this study examined the competencies of the mentioned key learning area for digital storytelling tools integration and using them for students' learning and development. Therefore, the manual analysis of the SNCECCE document was done to identify competencies of the SNCECCE's PSED domains that are suitable for digital storytelling integration. Based on appropriateness, pedagogical guidelines were suggested in two ways: Pedagogical guidelines for integrating digital storytelling tools such as video, audio, animation, written story, or e-book, and sound, with the PSED domains
Pedagogical guidelines for integrating digital storytelling tools for students' growth and education, including students' engagement, literacy skills, diverse learning styles, and technology integration, with the PSED domains

RESULT

This study focused on qualitative data by document analysis of the SNCECCE, Pakistan. The aim of selecting this document was to explore the competencies of the PSED domain for suitability. On the basis of appropriateness, this study recommended pedagogical guidelines for the integration of digital storytelling tools and their use for students' learning and development. The details of the analysis of the qualitative data are discussed in two parts:

The first part examines the suitability of the competencies of PSED domains for integrating digital storytelling tools and using them for students' growth and education.

The second part presents the pedagogical guidelines for the integration of digital storytelling tools and their use for students' growth as well as their education, with the PSED domains.

Part 1 – Suitability of Competencies of PSED Domains for DST integration

This domain has eight competencies focusing on children's likes, dislikes, emotional behavior, self-identity, sharing and working in pairs or groups, cultural and heritage appreciation, religious values, and practices. Civic sense, courtesy words, and ethical and moral values are also part of this area. This learning area consists of broad competencies and contains all three comprehensive developmental domains in one. This area allows children to work with others, adapting moral and religious values. Thus, the suitability of competencies of this learning area was analyzed in two ways: 1) Suitability for integrating digital storytelling tools such as video, audio, animation, written story, or ebook, and sound. 2) Suitability for integrating digital storytelling for the students' growth and education, including enhancing students' engagement,

improving literacy skills, supporting diverse learning styles, and integrating various technologies.

The suitability of the eight competencies of PSED domains for five digital storytelling tools is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Suitability of DST tools with PSED

Figure 1 presents that all tools of digital storytelling, including video, audio, written story or ebook, animation, and sound, are suitable for integration. However, a sound tool can be used separately or in combination with other tools.

The suitability of the eight competencies of PSED domains regarding DST integration for students' growth and learning purposes is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Suitability of DST for students' growth and learning with the PSED domain.

Part 2 –

integration with SNCECCE's PSED domain

As all competencies of PSED domains are suitable, thus, pedagogical guidelines are suggested for DST integration. Thus, Figure 3 represents the pedagogical guidelines for the integration of digital storytelling tools, including video, audio,

Figure 3: Pedagogical guidelines for DST tools with PSED.

Figure 3 proposes the pedagogical guidelines for integrating each tool of digital storytelling with all eight competencies of the PSED domain.

Similarly, pedagogical guidelines regarding DST integration for students' growth and learning are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Pedagogical Guidelines for DST integration for students' growth and education with PSED.

Figure 4 proposes the pedagogical guidelines towards the integration of digital storytelling for students' growth and learning with PSED domains.

DISCUSSION

This research applied a qualitative document analysis of the SNCECCE, Pakistan. The discussion of document analysis of the SNCECCE findings is presented in two ways:

Suitability and pedagogical guidelines for the integration of digital storytelling tools with SNCECCE's PSED domain

Suitability and pedagogical guidelines for the integration of digital storytelling for the purpose of students' learning and development, with SNCECCE's PSED domains

Suitability and pedagogical guidelines for digital storytelling tools integration

The results indicate the appropriateness and well-fitting of each DST tool with all the competencies of the PSED domains.

Video, a DST tool through which teachers can tell stories using visual features. The results show that video is the most suitable tool for integrating with all PSED's competencies. Teachers can use video-based stories in their classroom to provide a visual experience to the children that creates long long-lasting learning impact. Literature suggests that video simplifies complex problems and makes the abstract ideas easy for children (Rahiem, 2021; Griesser, 2001). As Rahiem (2021) mentioned that video video-based stories are helpful to boost the interest of children by providing graphical and visual effects. The findings regarding pedagogical guidelines for integrating video as a DST tool with the PSED domain indicate that video-based stories are helpful to provide visual effects to the children by aligning with all the competencies of this learning area using different modalities. The pedagogical guidelines provide teachers with multiple techniques to align DST with the competencies of the PSED domain. Developing short clips, scenario-based videos, illustrating the significance of concepts, etc, are some examples of creating video-based stories to express emotions, demonstrate the benefits of working together and sharing things, illustrate the significance of moral and religious values in our daily life, road rules, using courtesy words and expressions, etc. Numerous studies highlighted the use of video-based stories for promoting values, strengthening confidence, and coordination (Al-Barakat et al., 2025; Fajrie, 2025; Khan et al., 2025; Rahiem, 2021; O'Byrne et al., 2018). A sample story that could be created in relation to the competencies of moral values of helping each other is shown in Figure 5.

اتنے میں جنگل کے کچھ جانور وہاں آگئے اور انہوں نے چمکی کی مدد کرنے کا فیصلہ کیا۔

By then, some animals of the forest came and decided to help Chamki.

Figure 5: A Sample of video-based digital story

This sample consists of animated pictures, Urdu and English text, audio of story narration, and the sound of the animals. Through this way, children get the visual effect of the story, and it helps to develop skills that ultimately lead to achieving competencies in this learning area. Different software or apps, such as PowerPoint, Canva, Filmora, or Animato, etc can be used to create online video stories. While teachers can show video-based stories using different devices such as TV, multimedia, laptop or computer, or phone, depending on the facilities available (Catalano & Catalano, 2021).

Another DST tool is audio that provides children with verbal effects, which helps in enhancing listening and narrative skills. The document analysis shows that audio-based stories can be well-integrated with the SNCECCE's PSED domain. Thus, in the absence of the facility to show video-based stories, audio stories can be an excellent choice to integrate with this learning area in the ECE classroom. The pitch, intonation, and rhythm of the voice in audio stories create impact. Rahiem (2021) mentioned that the use of voices and various tones and rhythms can provide children with multiple experiences that lead to communication and language development. Further, this tool promotes listening skills as well as provides opportunities for children to enrich their imagination while listening. The findings regarding pedagogical guidelines suggested that teachers with various ways to integrate audio-based stories with all the competencies of the PSED in different ways. The verbal narration of stories, recording of step-by-step instructions for self-grooming, problem-solving, decision-making, and the narration of scenarios for applying religious and moral values in daily life are some examples. Many studies discussed the role of audio stories for promoting language, imagination, and creativity (Rahiem, 2021). Different software or apps can be used for recording audio-based stories, such as a voice recorder on a phone, laptop, or computer, the Audacity app, etc. Teachers can use audio-based

stories using different devices such as TV, multimedia, laptop or computer, or phone, based on available facilities (Catalano & Catalano, 2021). Moreover, in such cases, where facilities to show video stories are not available, the audio of the story is an excellent alternative.

A written story or e-book consists of the text or images of stories presented in digital form using various software or apps. This tool allows children to access, read, and explore stories or pictures at any time and at their convenience. This tool also provides opportunities for the children to highlight the texts using different features, like bookmark, highlighter tools to mark new vocabulary, etc. The findings indicate the suitability of integrating this tool with the SNCECCE's PSED domain. Literature suggests that this tool is helpful for emergent readers or learners by offering them e-experiences (Delahey Childcare, 2024). The findings regarding pedagogical guidelines to integrate written stories or e-books PSED domain revealed many suggestions to the teachers to use the digital written story or e-book in their classroom. For instance, writing the script of stories for online reading, inserting pictures for analyzing, using read-aloud features for narrating the text of the stories, etc, are some strategies that are integrated to emphasize the significance of working together, civic rules, aspects of cultural and heritages, and so forth. Figure 6 illustrates a sample written story, which contains Urdu and English text along with pictures.

Figure 6: A Sample of a Written Story

Numerous studies exhibited the role of written stories or e-books for language enhancement, mathematical concepts, and scientific inquiry (Rahiem, 2021). Teachers can use a soft version of stories available online and can write and illustrate pictures using different software or apps such as MS documents, PowerPoint, Canva, publishers, etc. Teachers can share the written story or eBooks using online tools or in PDF or image form for easy access by children. Moreover, if teachers do not have facilities to show video or audio stories, written stories, or e-books can be helpful to share with children for their easy access at their own time and pace.

The next tool is animation, which adds movement and actions to still pictures and text, making the stories more interactive. This tool is also helpful in creating animated games and activities along with stories that enhance imagination and bring out visual thinking to the reality in children. The results indicate the appropriateness of animation with all the competencies of SNCECCE's PSED domain. Findings regarding pedagogical guidelines to integrate animation-based digital storytelling with

the PSED domain indicate that this tool is appropriately linked with all competencies. Guidelines suggested many ways to use animation in the ECE classroom. For instance, developing animated games, activities, movies, and stories for creatively demonstrating different emotions, behaviors, and values, illustrating cultural and religious aspects, civic values, self-identity, and working with others in collaboration, etc Rare studies are available highlighting the use of animation-based stories and their benefits. This study provided the techniques to the teachers for integrating this tool with key learning areas. A sample animated game is shown in Figure 7. This game promotes reading skills in children by allowing them to read cues. It encourages movement through clicking the relevant pictures and develops the value of gratitude for their PSED.

Figure 7: A sample of an animated game

Teachers can use different tools and apps to add animation in stories, such as PowerPoint, Paint, Animator, Canva, Illustrator, etc. However, this tool can bring life to video-based stories as well as create activities and games in association with digital stories.

The last tool is sound, it is a very important tool of digital storytelling, which brings effects to the stories by adding background tunes, music, rhythms, as well as voices of different objects such as vehicles, communication, water, etc, and creatures like animals, birds, insects, reptiles, human beings, and other species etc. This tool is different from the audio-based stories as it uses sound effects, voices, tunes, and rhythm in the stories. The findings from the document analysis of SNCECCE entail that this tool is suitable for all competencies of the PSED domain, either separately or in combination with other tools such as video, audio, or a written story or e-book. The findings regarding pedagogical guidelines to integrate sound-based digital storytelling with PSED show that sound tools can be integrated either independently or combined with video, audio, and written story or e-books DST tools. The sound of different emotions, such as laughing, crying, etc., the sound of cultural music, and tunes using

different musical instruments, the tunes and music of religious hymns and songs are some examples. A limited number of studies have discussed the significance of a sound tool. Undheim (2020) in the study highlighted the importance of using sound in digital stories. Thus, the study analyzed the integration of a sound tool with key learning areas. Teachers can use different tools and apps to add sound to the stories, such as online sound tools, PowerPoint, movie makers, etc. Teachers can use their phones, computers, laptops, players, etc, in the classroom for sound-based stories.

Suitability and pedagogical guidelines for digital storytelling integration for students' learning and development

The study also analyzed the suitability and pedagogical guidelines for DST integration for the purpose of students' learning and development, such as enhancing students' engagement, improving literacy skills, supporting diverse learning styles, and integrating various technologies.

The first aim of digital storytelling integration is to enhance students' engagement. This purpose has a dual role; First, it allows children to engage in different tasks and activities by prompting questions and instructions during and after the stories. The second way is that it involves children in creating digital stories by allotting them various characters and roles, as well as providing opportunities to record their voices for story narration. The findings reveal that DST is suitable to integrate with the PSED domain and allows children to engage actively in the creation of stories as well as to complete the tasks and activities. Numerous studies mentioned the engagement of students for creating digital stories by boosting their motivation, interest, and comprehension (O'Byrne et al, 2018; Smeda, Dakich, & Sharda, 2014). The findings regarding pedagogical guidelines for DST integration with seven key learning areas suggested multiple ways for teachers to engage students in the ECE classroom. For instance, predicting the story, analyzing the picture, reading the text, sharing views, working with peers, demonstrating ethical value, environmental responsibilities, and exploring different aspects of cultures, such as dresses, languages, and foods, are some examples to engage children. Thus, the guidelines have provided practical tips to the teachers for students' engagement through digital stories. Teachers can engage students either before, during, or after the stories by providing opportunities to read the story, make predictions, allocate tasks, etc.

Another purpose of digital storytelling integration is to improve literacy skills. Digital stories employ various means such as images, texts, and audio to strengthen the literacy skills of the children. Thus, the digital stories can be used in multiple ways to promote reading, listening, writing, and speaking skills of children. The findings indicate that digital stories are viable for improving the literacy skills of children by providing visual, oral, and graphic experiences with SNCECCE's PSED domain. Literature also suggests that digital stories give powerful learning experiences that promote language, understanding, and observation in the early years (Rahiem, 2021; Robin, 2008). Many studies explored the impact of digital storytelling for literacy skills improvement through communication, expression, and interpersonal skills (Liu et al, 2024; Rahiem, 2021; Robin, 2016; Sadik, 2008). The findings of the analysis of pedagogical guidelines towards digital storytelling integration for the purpose of literacy skills improvement indicate that digital storytelling can well-integrate with all competencies of the PSED for given purposes. The reading of text, analyzing pictures, listening to the stories attentively, sharing views through writing and speaking, are some of the ways for literacy improvement. Digital stories can be integrated by creating stories to demonstrate different languages, moral and religious values,

naming, and features of different cultural and heritage aspects, using courtesy words, and so forth.

The suitability of DST integration for the purpose of supporting diverse learning styles was also analyzed. This purpose caters to the requirements of all types of learners, including visual, auditory, reading or writing, kinesthetic, and social. DST uses different modalities such as visual, audio, images, text, movement, and activities to facilitate these different learners' needs. The result shows that DST is well-fitted for meeting the diverse needs of children by exposing them to different ways of learning. Thus, the objective of using digital stories in the classroom to support the various needs of learners is well-achieved by aligning with the SNCECCE's PSED domain. Robin (2016), in his study, mentioned the use of visual images, text, audio, and other elements with digital stories. Numerous studies highlighted the use of digital storytelling for teaching and learning purposes; however, using digital storytelling for the purpose of supporting diverse learning styles was unexplored. The findings regarding pedagogical guidelines towards integration of digital storytelling for the purpose of supporting diverse learning styles suggested distinct ways to integrate with the PSED domain. Digital stories use visual, oral, text, and activities for different emotional expression, moral and religious values, courtesy words and expressions, road signs and rules, different foods, lifestyles, and dresses in diverse cultures and heritages, and so forth. Thus, digital storytelling is worthwhile for diverse learners as it fulfills their needs. Teachers can use different modalities to include all kinds of learners in their classroom and provide varied experiences to the children.

The fourth purpose of DST integration is to use a variety of technologies in the ECE classroom. Digital technologies, either in hardware or software, are useful for incorporating digital stories in the classroom. These devices could be a phone, camera, radio, laptop, etc, as well as software like MS Office, Canva, paint, online games, etc. The analysis entails that technology-based digital stories are suitable for all competencies of the PSED. Numerous studies are available highlighting the significance of technologies or devices for digital stories. For instance, Rahiem (2021) mentioned the use of PowerPoint and Multimedia for telling stories in the classroom, which makes the stories "more entertaining, captivating, engaging, communicative, and theatrical". Merjovaara, Nousiainen, Turja & Isotalo (2020) discussed the use of technologies for digital storytelling for active participation of children in the classroom and for imparting 21st-century skills in children. The findings present the pedagogical guidelines for digital storytelling integration for the purpose of integrating various technologies with the PSED domain. Devices or technologies can be used for expressing emotions, demonstrating moral and religious values, as well as civic and environmental responsibilities in different scenarios, pictures of different cultural and heritage aspects, etc. Moreover, the tasks for working in a group using technologies can be assigned to the children. Therefore, teachers can use and explore technologies to provide different experiences to the children by encouraging them through digital stories. Thus, teachers can create stories for the utilization of technologies and use technology-based stories in their classroom. Sadik (2008), in his study, shared the example of integrating Ms. Photo Story for creating stories with children by applying some editorial and production skills.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to find the competencies of SNCECCE's PSED domain for crafting pedagogical guidelines for effective integration of digital storytelling tools and using them for students' learning and development in the Early Childhood Education

classrooms in Pakistan. This study concluded that all competencies of the PSED domain are suitable for digital storytelling integration in terms of their tools and using them for students' learning and development. To achieve effective integration of digital storytelling in the classroom, this study crafted pedagogical guidelines especially for integrating digital storytelling tools such as video, audio, written story, e-book, and sound. The detailed pedagogical guidelines also suggested integrating digital storytelling for the specific purposes of students' learning and development, including enhancing students' engagement, improving literacy skills, supporting diverse needs of learning styles, and integrating various technologies with the PSED. Therefore, the pedagogical guidelines serve as a filler to ensure the effective utilization of digital storytelling at the ECE level.

This research contributes to education at large and supports policymakers, curriculum developers, teachers, and practitioners to integrate digital stories in teaching and learning practices in the Early Childhood Education classroom. Thus, this study supports policy makers and curriculum developers in three ways:

It helps to redesign the educational framework by integrating digital storytelling into the curriculum. The integration of various tools and using them for the purposes of students' learning and development brings innovation in the curriculum implementation.

It contributes to revamping the infrastructure of the Early Childhood classroom by providing facilities that require digital storytelling tool integration. For instance, LED, multimedia, laptop, or computers for video or animated stories, speakers for audio or sound-based stories, etc.

It supports designing the training programmes for teachers' capacity building based on the pedagogical guidelines recommended towards integration of various digital storytelling tools, and for students' learning and development purposes.

This study also contributes to the teachers and practitioners affiliated with the Early Childhood Education level in the following ways:

It guides teachers to integrate various tools of digital storytelling in their classroom and for the purposes of students' learning and development.

The pedagogical guidelines recommended in this study support them to align digital storytelling with SNCECCE's PSED domain by incorporating suggested activities and ways in their teaching and learning practices.

It supports them to enhance the students' engagement, improve their literacy skills, support the diverse needs of learners, and integrate various technologies through pedagogical guidelines regarding digital storytelling integration.

It enhances the capacities of teachers to bring digital transformation in their teaching and learning processes through the optimal utilization of digital storytelling in their classrooms.

This study concludes that the integration of digital storytelling can transform conventional learning experiences into long-lasting, meaningful digital learning imprints. The suggested pedagogical guidelines ensure the optimal integration of digital storytelling tools and their use for students' growth and learning purposes in the ECE classrooms within the Pakistani context.

This study explores potential areas for future research based on its findings; the following are some recommendations for further studies:

Future studies can explore the integration of digital stories with existing curriculum available or taught in Pakistani schools in different contexts.

Pedagogical guidelines can extend to add more purposes for students' learning and development, particularly including holistic developmental domains.

Pedagogical guidelines can suggest providing a conducive environment to the children, and redesigning the framework for the teacher training programme by integrating DST.

The experimental or action research can be conducted to observe the impact of DST integration on students' learning and development through control group strategies and classroom observations.

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